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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Atopy is defined as an individual or familial history of type 1 allergy, bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis-conjunctivitis and/or atopic dermatitis and/or a tendency to overproduce IgE antibodies (Weidinger & Novak, 2015). Asthma, allergic rhinitis, food allergy and atopic dermatitis are typically considered allergic diseases. Allergic March - Atopic March is a concept that refers to the natural progression of allergic diseases that usually begin early in life. The order of disease progression in childhood is usually Atopic Dermatitis, Food Allergy, Allergic Rhinitis, Asthma. This progression, which continues as skin, gastrointestinal system, respiratory system, may change depending on genetic and environmental exposure, possibly through epigenetic mechanisms (Turner, 2017). The main problem is inflammation caused by dysregulation of the immune response dependent on T helper 2 (Th2) cells (Martín-Orozco, Norte-Muñoz, & Martínez-García, 2017).

Materials and Methods: Possible mechanisms for the Allergic March are described as dysfunction of the skin barrier, alterations in the microbiome, epigenetic factors, social dysfunction of cells and molecules and the predicted interaction of other genes (Hill & Spergel, 2018; Hirota et al., 2017; Hudson, 2006; Luo, 2010; Penders et al., 2006; Peng et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2020).

Results: Atopic dermatitis is a chronic inflammatory skin disease characterised by recurrent itching and impaired skin barrier. 45% of affected children are diagnosed before the age of 6 months, 60% before the age of 1 year and 85% before the age of 5 years (Spergel, 2005). Food allergy (IgE positive) usually occurs in childhood with atopic dermatitis as the earliest manifestation of atopic march, with an estimated prevalence of 6-8% (Torres et al., 2019; Yang, Fu, & Zhou, 2020). It usually presents with mild symptoms such as abdominal discomfort, nausea, vomiting or diarrhoea (Knyziak-Mędrzycka, Majsiak, & Cukrowska, 2023). Eosinophilic esophagitis is defined as an immunological (Th2) disease causing chronic esophageal dysfunction characterised histologically by eosinophilic inflammation. Although it has been hypothesised that eosinophilic oesophagitis is the fifth member of the atopic march, this is controversial (Mohammad et al., 2017).

Conclusion: Strategically, it is important to consider that breastfeeding for more than 6 months not only reduces the incidence of atopic dermatitis but also reduces the risk of developing other allergic diseases, that the use of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* as a probiotic during the first 2 years of life can be effective, that the use of tobacco products at home or in the environment triggers the development of allergic sensitisation - asthma in children and that the prevention of exposure is strongly ensured (Dick et al., 2014; Kull et al., 2005; Wickens et al., 2008). According to the Allergic March theory, early recognition of children at risk of allergic diseases and prevention of the process will significantly improve the quality of life in a healthy adult.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Asthma, rhinitis allergic, food allergies, atopic dermatitis, allergy

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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